

THE MEANING AND IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING MENTAL ABILITIES OF CHILDREN OF JUNIOR SCHOOL AGE

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Annotation: This article describes the methods and methods of developing students' mental abilities and how to use them, as well as ways to develop their life skills. Today, great attention is paid to the development of the scientific potential of young people. You can find out from the information given below. In a word, attention to youth is attention to the future.

Key words: intellectual education, spiritual and moral requirements, state policy, scientific and professional knowledge, worldview, nature, social society, thinking and personal activity.

Today, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to mental education of young people. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ORQ-637 dated 23.09.2020 "On Education", together with the decisions made in recent years, educate highly qualified personnel who meet high moral and ethical requirements it is emphasized that it is one of the priority directions of the state policy. Becoming a highly qualified staff meeting high moral and ethical requirements means thorough acquisition of available scientific and professional knowledge. Therefore, having deep knowledge allows to understand the essence of natural and social processes, to see and evaluate their positive and negative aspects. At this point, worldview is also important in the development of thinking and personal activity of a young child.

A worldview is a system of dialectical views and beliefs that determine the development of the content of nature, social society, thinking and personal activity. Beliefs formed on the basis of socio-ideological, philosophical, economic, natural-

scientific, spiritual-ethical, aesthetic, legal and ecological knowledge appear as the main structural elements within this system.

Having a certain worldview is a person's determination of a certain attitude towards the environment, social relations, labor activity and production process, subjects, as well as a full understanding of the social duties undertaken by a person and responsibility for fulfilling them. creates the ground for having a feeling.

Establishing a consistent, systematic, continuous and goal-oriented education in young children, their active participation in the process of social relations of various directions and content, as well as self-education formed as a result. In the formation of the worldview of the young generation, it is important for them to master the fundamentals of natural, social and humanitarian sciences taught in educational institutions.

The spiritual and moral image of a person, his life approaches, the essence of the values and moral principles that are of priority to him represent the content of his worldview. On the other hand, the enrichment of the worldview ensures the gradual stabilization of personal qualities and qualities of a person. A worldview that expresses good ideas in its content helps to enrich the positive qualities manifested in the image of a person.

According to its essence, the worldview differs in scientific (having a certain philosophical system) and simple (not having a certain philosophical system) worldview. The scientific worldview is based on ideas that have gained stability as a result of continuous and consistent mastering the basics of existing sciences, active participation in the process of social relations.

The formation of a person's worldview is a long-term, complex process with a dynamic nature.

The main signs and essence of intellectual education and scientific outlook. Mental education plays an important role in the formation of a person's outlook.

Mental education is a pedagogical activity aimed at giving a person knowledge about nature and the development of society, forming his mental (cognitive) ability, thinking, and based on its effective implementation, a worldview is formed.

Acquaintance of students with achievements in the fields of science, technology, technology, and production creates a basis for developing creative, free, and independent thinking skills.

In the process of mental education, the following tasks are solved:

Giving students scientific knowledge.

1. Establishing a conscious attitude towards acquiring scientific knowledge in them.
2. Formation of skills and qualifications of using existing knowledge in practice.
3. Forming a sense of striving to constantly enrich one's knowledge.
4. Psychological abilities (speech, attention, memory, thinking, creative imagination) and characteristics (striving for a specific goal, curiosity, observation, independent thinking, creative thinking, justifying one's opinion, using available information) that help to acquire knowledge generalization, grouping, drawing logical conclusions, etc.).

On the basis of the unity of mental education and upbringing, thinking (full reflection of social events in the mind, a high form of human intellectual activity) develops in a person. According to sources, determining the current level of mental thinking is somewhat complicated and can be determined according to the following signs:

1. Existence of scientific knowledge system.
2. The process of acquiring existing scientific knowledge.
3. Possession of thinking skills.
4. The emergence of interest and need to acquire knowledge.

Brainstorming is the result of long-term and relentless research. Scientific view and belief have a special place in its formation.

A scientific point of view is a scientifically based opinion, an idea that sheds light on the essence of a certain phenomenon, process, and when a person has thoroughly mastered the existing system of scientific knowledge, he can compare and contrast knowledge with each other, analyze the essence of an object, phenomenon or process. occurs as a result. Teaching students to think creatively, forming inventive skills creates a basis for them to conduct scientific research and advance certain scientific views.

Effective organization of intellectual education ensures the emergence of scientific thinking in a person.

Scientific thinking is considered the highest form of human mental activity and means a scientific approach to social events and processes.

There are several acceptable forms, methods and means of forming the student's outlook, including conversations, debates, lectures on spiritual-ethical, socio-ideological, economic, legal, aesthetic and ecological topics. practical trainings, debates, independence, as well as business games that encourage students to think on the basis of creating problem situations are considered more effective.

Organizing independent work, in particular, guiding students to conduct small scientific research on a specific topic, serves as a foundation for further enriching their worldviews.

Encouraging teenagers and young adults to express a critical attitude towards the ideas of certain theories or teachings, reveal their methodological essence, and encourage them to work based on valid evidence in expressing their personal opinions.

The consistent, continuous, systematic organization of the educational process based on a clear social goal, in this process, interrelationship between disciplines, as well as working based on the unity of all existing factors that are effective in the formation of worldview, is a guarantee of achieving the intended goal.

This situation makes it possible to evaluate the essence of certain social events from different perspectives, to be able to see their development, to observe their transition from one state to another, to understand their interdependence and connection, and their need for each other.

In the process of organizing education, it is desirable to strive to make effective use of the possibilities of achieving personal maturity under the influence of the interrelationship of disciplines, social and natural factors, environment and social relations.

In-depth learning by students of the basics of subjects recommended as educational subjects in educational institutions helps to form a broad worldview in them.

It is necessary for teachers to take care of the formation of a scientific worldview in students and to constantly pay attention to the practical application of the scientific knowledge acquired by them.

Science teachers, while introducing students to one or another laws and their essence, should explain to students the need to use them or work based on them in various life situations.

It is important to be fully aware of the ideological ideas that have a priority place in the society and their essence in the formation of the worldview. Therefore, in the process of introducing students to the essence of education and upbringing, in particular, the foundations of social, humanitarian and natural sciences, national independence, which is recognized as the main criterion in the social life of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is a pedagogically effective way to provide detailed information about the views advanced in the content of the school and ideology, and to form a certain attitude of students towards them.

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